

SYNTHETIC INVESTIGATIONS IN DICYCLOHEXANE DERIVATIVES. PART II

BY PASUPATI SEN-GUPTA AND BIDYUT KAMAL BHATTACHARYYA

Ethyl 1-cyano cyclohexylcyanoacetate on condensation with ethyl β -bromovalerate, followed by hydrolysis and esterification furnishes ethyl α -(1-carboethoxy-cyclohexyl)-pimelate which on Dieckmann condensation, hydrolysis and esterification yields 2-keto-1'-carboethoxydicyclohexane. 1-(1'-Carboxy-cyclohexyl)-2-carboxy- Δ^1 -cyclohexene is obtained through the cyanohydrin of the above keto-ester.

Marvel *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 972) claimed to have synthesised Δ^{11} -dodecahydro-9-phenanthrone by the cyclisation of the dienyne (I) with 85% formic acid. But Levitz, Perlmann and Bogert (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1941, 105) from a study of spiro-(cyclohexane-1:1'-indan) suggested that the ketone possessed a spirane skeleton, which rearranged to phenanthrene derivatives under the conditions of dehydrogenation.

Linstead *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 842 ; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1996) oxidised the saturated ketone formed by hydrogenation of Marvel's ketone with nitric acid and obtained a dibasic acid to which structure (II) has been proposed.

The synthesis of this dicarboxylic acid (II) has been attempted along the following line.

cycloHexanone has been condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate according to Cope's modification of Knoevenagel's reaction (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3452). Hydrocyanic acid adds to the ethyl cyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate (Hope and Sheldon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2223) to yield ethyl 1-cyanocyclohexyl-cyanoacetate in an excellent yield. The same dicyano-ester was also prepared by Dickens, Horton and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1830) by condensing cyclohexanone cyanohydrin with ethyl sodio-cyanoacetate, but the yield in the present method is better. The condensation of β -bromovaleric ester with the above dicyano-ester has been effected in alcoholic solution in presence of sodium ethoxide when ethyl α -(1-cyanocyclohexyl)- α -cyanopimelate (III, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{CN}$; $R_3 = \text{Et}$) is formed. The above condensation cannot be effected with potassium dust in xylene solution. The dicyano-ester (III, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{CN}$; $R_3 = \text{Et}$) has been hydrolysed by refluxing first with 70% sulphuric acid and then with 20% aqueous alkali when α -(1-carboxycyclohexyl)-pimelic acid (III, $R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{H}$; $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$) is obtained. The ethyl ester of this α -substituted pimelic acid (III, $R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{Et}$) after ring-closure by Dieckmann's method furnishes a β -keto-ester (IV, $R_1 = \text{Et}$;

$R_2 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) which on hydrolysis with a mixture of acetic acid, concentrated hydrochloric acid and water yields 1'-carboxy-2-keto-dicyclohexane (IV, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$).

The cyanohydrin of the ethyl ester of the keto-acid (IV, $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$) has been prepared according to the method of Ultee (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1909, 28, 1). The yield is very low due to steric hindrance in the molecule. The cyanohydrin on dehydration by the addition of thionyl chloride and pyridine furnishes 1-(1'-carboethoxy)-cyclohexyl-2-cyan- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (V, $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{CN}$). Attempts to effect the hydrolysis of this unsaturated nitrile with 80% phosphoric acid, with a mixture of acetic acid, sulphuric acid and water or with 20% aqueous caustic potash in an atmosphere of nitrogen proved futile. On hydrolysis with 70% sulphuric acid, followed by a 25% aqueous caustic potash solution 1-(1'-carboxycyclohexyl)-2-carboxy- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (V, $R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{CO}_2\text{H}$) of m. p. 157-59° is obtained. But due to the very low yield the next step i. e., catalytic hydrogenation to dicyclohexyl-1:2'-dicarboxylic acid could not be effected.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl 1-Cyanocyclohexylcyanoacetate.—Ethyl cyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate (69 g.) was dissolved in rectified spirit (430 c. c.). Potassium cyanide (46.8 g.) in water (252 c. c.) was added to the ester dropwise. To the cold mixture was added hydrochloric acid (57.3 c. c.) with water (40.3 c. c.) at 10°. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (114.6 c. c.) and powdered ice were added to the reaction mixture when ethyl 1-cyanocyclohexylcyanoacetate was precipitated; it was extracted with ether, dried and distilled, b. p. 165-168°/4-5 mm., yield 64 g. A small portion was crystallised from low boiling petroleum ether in fine prism-like crystals, m. p. 48°. (Found: C, 65.08; H, 7.29. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires C, 65.45; H, 7.27 per cent).

Ethyl α -(1-Cyanocyclohexyl)- α -cyanopimelate (III, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{CN}$; $R_3 = \text{Et}$).—Ethyl 1-cyanocyclohexylcyanoacetate (57 g.), dissolved in alcohol (57 c. c.) was added to sodium ethoxide (prepared by dissolving 5.9 g. sodium in 200 c. c. of absolute alcohol), cooled in a freezing mixture and the reaction mixture was kept in the freezing mixture for half an hour. Then ethyl δ -bromovalerate (80 g.) was added and refluxed for 24 hours. The condensation product was treated with ice-water, extracted with ether and distilled, b. p. 220°/3 mm., yield 53 g. (Found: C, 64.95; H, 8.11. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires C, 65.52; H, 8.05 per cent).

α -(1-Carboxycyclohexyl)-pimelic Acid (III, $R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{H}$; $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$).—The above dicyano-ester (53 g.) was refluxed gently for 4 hours with a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid (265 c. c.), acetic acid (185.5 c. c.) and water (79.5 c. c.). A considerable portion carbonised. The product was distilled with steam to drive away acetic acid and extracted with ether after dilution with ice-water. The product still contained nitrogen and it was further refluxed for 30 hours with caustic potash (75 g.) in water (210 c. c.). The product was acidified with concentrated sulphuric acid (40 c. c.) in ice-water, extracted with ether and dried. After removing ether the residue solidified in a vacuum desiccator. The crude solid was crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 152° , yield 26 g.

The hydrolysis of the same dicyano-ester was effected in a better yield with 70% sulphuric acid. The dicyano-ester (30 g.) was refluxed for 12 hours with concentrated sulphuric acid (105 c. c.) and water (90 c. c.). The reaction product was diluted with ice-water, extracted as usual and further refluxed for 30 hours with caustic potash (75 g.) in water (225 c. c.). The product was worked up in the usual way, yield 22 g. (Found: C 58.8; H, 7.8. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 58.74; H, 7.69 per cent).

Ethyl α -(1-Carboxycyclohexyl)-pimelate ($R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{Et}$).—The above tribasic acid (26 g.) was esterified by refluxing on the water-bath for 70 hours with ethyl alcohol (100 c. c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.14, 18 c. c.). The product was diluted with ice-water, extracted with ether and distilled, b. p. $190^\circ/3$ mm., yield 19 g. (Found: C, 64.72; H, 8.92. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 64.8; H, 9.19 per cent).

2-Keto-1':3-dicarbethoxy-dicyclohexane (IV, $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$).—Ethyl α -(1-carbethoxycyclohexyl)-pimelate (19 g.) was refluxed in dry benzene (50 c. c.) with sodium dust (2.3 g.) and dry ethyl alcohol (3 c. c.) for 18 hours on a water-bath. The product was treated with sulphuric acid (6 c. c.) in ice. The β -keto-ester was extracted with benzene and distilled, while a portion decomposed, b. p. $178\text{--}186^\circ/5\text{--}6$ mm., yield 12 g. (Found: C, 68.6; H, 8.6. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 66.6; H, 8.64 per cent). The deviation is due to the decomposition of the β -keto-ester during distillation.

2-Keto-1'-carbethoxydicyclohexane (IV, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$).—(a) The above β -keto-ester (12 g.) was refluxed with 20% sulphuric acid (100 c. c.) for 20 hours. The product still contained portions insoluble in alkali. It was further refluxed for 4 hours with caustic potash (10 g.), methanol (50 c. c.) and water (10 c. c.). The reaction mixture was acidified and extracted with ether. On removing ether the crude product containing 2-keto-1'-carboxydicyclohexane was esterified by refluxing for 30 hours on the water-bath with ethyl alcohol (50 c. c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 5 c. c.). The product was worked up as usual, from which 2-keto-1'-carbethoxydicyclohexane was distilled, b. p. $136^\circ/3$ mm., yield, 6.5 g.

(b) A better method was to reflux the above β -keto-ester (20 g.) with acetic acid (125 c. c.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (62.5 c. c.) and water (12.5 c. c.) for 24 hours. The extraction and esterification of the crude acid was the same as described above, b. p. $165\text{--}168$ mm., yield 9.3 g. (Found: C, 70.74; H, 9.5. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 71.42; H, 9.52 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-2-cyano-1'-carbethoxydicyclohexane.—(a). The preparation of the cyano-hydrin was first attempted according to the method of Butenandt, Schmidt and Thome (*Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1487) but without success.

(b) Dry hydrogen cyanide was passed into the above keto-ester (3.8 g) taken in a test tube with a drop of aqueous potassium cyanide solution and cooled below -10° . When in the test-tube there were two layers; it was corked, the contents were thoroughly mixed and left overnight in a refrigerator. After adding one drop of sulphuric acid hydrogen cyanide was driven off from the product, which was then extracted with ether. The cyanohydrin was crystallised from petroleum ether, m. p. $87-88^{\circ}$, yield 0.89 g. (Found: C, 69.21; H, 9.18. $C_{14}H_{25}O_3N$ requires C, 68.8; H, 8.97 per cent).

1-(1'-Carboxycyclohexyl)-2-carboxy- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (V, $R_1 = Et$; $R_2 = CN$).—The above cyanohydrin (0.6 g.) was dehydrated in pyridine (0.7 c.c.), cooled in ice by the addition of thionyl chloride (0.33 c.c.) drop by drop and refluxing for 2 hours on a water-bath after leaving the reaction mixture overnight. The product was acidified with hydrochloric acid (2 c.c.) in ice, extracted with ether and 1-(1'-carboxycyclohexyl)-2-cyano- Δ^1 -cyclohexene was distilled, b.p. $165^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 0.45 g.

(a) The unsaturated cyano-ester (1.4 g.) was refluxed for 10 hours with phosphoric acid (16 c.c.) in water (4 c.c.). But no hydrolysis could be effected by this method.

(b) The unsaturated cyano-ester (1.4 g.) was refluxed for 10 hours with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.), acetic acid (7 c.c.) and water (3 c.c.). The product carbonised and no acid could be isolated from it.

(c) The cyano-ester (1.2 g.) was next refluxed for 8 hours with 70% sulphuric acid (12 c.c.). The product still contained nitrogen. The crude product was further refluxed with 25% aqueous caustic potash (20 c.c.) for 24 hours. The product was acidified and extracted as usual. After dissolving the product in acetic acid a few crystals of 1-(1'-carboxycyclohexyl)-2-carboxy- Δ^1 -cyclohexene, of m. p. $157-59^{\circ}$ were obtained, but the yield was unsatisfactory. (Found: C, 66.58; H, 7.92. $C_{14}H_{25}O_3$ requires C, 66.66; H, 7.93 per cent).

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SIR P. C. RAY RESEARCH FELLOW'S LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA 9.

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